

AUTHORITY OPTIMISATION FOR RESONANT MORPHING CONTROL OF BI-STABLE WING-SHAPED COMPOSITES

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Abstract

Bi-stable composites have attracted attention from the adaptive structures community thanks to their ability to exhibit two statically stable shapes. To exert controlled changes between the stable configurations, large deflections leading to a phenomenon known as snap-through need to be triggered. Recently, a resonant actuation technique achieving full configuration control for bi-stable composites using distributed piezoelectric actuators has been introduced. In this paper, the optimal positioning of piezoelectric actuators for applying resonant configuration control on wing-shaped bi-stable composites is studied. An analytical model for the dynamic response of wing-shaped bi-stable composites is presented allowing for the calculating modal characteristics required to apply the resonant control strategy. The variation of the generalised electromechanical coupling coefficient with respect to the position of the piezoelectric actuators is studied to obtain maximum authority over different vibration modes with the resonant control technique for wing-shaped bi-stable composites.

Keywords: Bi-stable wing, unsymmetric composites, morphing, snap-through, piezoelectric

1 Introduction

Bi-stable composites have attracted the attention from the adaptive structures community due to their ability to statically hold two stable configurations without requiring continuous actuation effort [1]. As a result, large conformal deformation, or morphing, can be achieved by exploiting the difference exhibited by the stable geometries with minimal energy requirements. Spatially distributed smart material actuators, such as piezoelectric composite layers, are highly desirable to actuate over bi-stable laminates due to their ease of integration with composite structures, as well as for their wide frequency bandwidth. However, current piezoelectric actuators lack sufficient authority to exert full configuration control using conventional quasi-static strategies on bi-stable composites [2]. This problem has been addressed by introducing a resonant control strategy which exploits the inertia of the laminates through excitation of targeted modal frequencies [3, 4]. Large deflections are in-

duced until the composite deflects past a critical displacement threshold, after which a change between stable states, or snap-through, follows [5]. Once a snap-through is triggered the plate remains in the newly attained state as the difference between the modal frequencies associated to each state results in off-resonance response, i.e. low amplitude residual response. The implementation of the resonant strategy allows to employ highly embedded distributed actuation systems to achieve configuration control between the stable states. This control concept has been demonstrated for a wing-shaped bi-stable composite specimen subjected to aerodynamic loads in wind tunnel tests [6].

In this investigation, the design of the actuation positioning on wing-shaped bi-stable composites to minimise the control input for triggering controlled changes of state, i.e. snap-through, with surface bonded piezoelectric composite layers is investigated. In particular, this study focuses on selecting the most adequate positioning of the actuators using theoretically obtained modal characteristics of

the wing-shaped structures. To this end, an analytical model for the dynamics of wing-shaped bi-stable composites is used to obtain modal frequencies and mode shapes [7]. The generalised electromechanical coupling coefficient, associated to the modes excited in the resonant control strategy, are maximised for obtaining largest possible actuation authority. By maximising the generalised coupling coefficient associated to a mode exhibiting a compatible deformation shape for reaching the critical displacement threshold, the resulting control authority is maximised. This allows to achieve full configuration control for triggering desired changes of state, while minimising the required actuation effort.

2 Modelling of Bi-stable Composites

In this study, laminates with a tapered planform, hereafter referred as wing-shaped bi-stable composites, arranged in a cantilever configuration are considered. Wing-shaped bi-stable composites have been studied in the past as morphing winglets for enhanced lift [8] and passive load alleviation [9]. To achieve this, a tailored lay-up combining symmetrical and unsymmetrical stacking sequences is used [10]. For the type of composites studied in this investigation, bi-stability arises due to thermal stresses resulting from a mismatch between the thermal expansion coefficients of the fibres and the epoxy matrix induced during cooling process after elevated temperature curing in the unsymmetrically laminated part [11]. Piezoelectric composite actuators exploiting the higher d_{33} coefficient, known as Macro-Fiber Composites (MFC), are implemented in this investigation to exert configuration control on the wing-shaped bi-stable composite.

Forcing a large deflection on a bi-stable composite results in a sudden jump to the second stable state, known as snap-through. This occurs when a given level of deflection is forced upon the composite, known as critical displacement, after which snap-through follows [5]. The critical displacement threshold is defined as the out-of-plane displacement of each state from the original flat shape, which results in a different value for each stable state as schematically shown in Fig. 1. The authority of the piezoelectric actuators needs to be sufficient for inducing this deflection on the wing-

Figure 1: Stable states and critical displacement for a cantilevered bi-stable composite.

shaped composites. To achieve this, while minimising the voltage input, the position of the actuators is optimised by maximising the generalised electromechanical coupling coefficient. This suits the resonant control technique, as the maximisation of the coefficient yields the highest possible actuation coupling to a particular mode. In the following sections a brief account is given presenting the necessary steps for deriving the analytical model used to carry out the design of the modal properties for minimising the actuation effort for wing-shaped bi-stable composites. For a detailed account of the model derivation please refer to Ref. [7].

2.1 Variational Formulation

A variational formulation is followed for the calculation of the final equilibrium shapes and the associated dynamic response of the studied wing-shaped bi-stable composites is presented. The Lagrangian, \mathcal{L} , for a bi-stable composite is equivalent to that of a cross-ply unsymmetrically laminated plate given by:

$$\mathcal{L} = T - U + \mathcal{W}_{ext}, \quad (1)$$

where T , U are the kinetic and potential energies, and \mathcal{W}_{ext} is the work done by external energy, respectively.

The kinetic energy of the system is the sum of the kinetic energy of the composite and the piezoelectric elements, given by:

$$T_{st} = \frac{1}{2} \int_{V_s} \rho \dot{\mathbf{u}}' \dot{\mathbf{u}} dV_s, \quad (2)$$

and

$$T_{pzt} = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{l=1}^{N_{pzt}} \int_{V_p^{(l)}} \rho_{pzt} \dot{\mathbf{u}}' \dot{\mathbf{u}} dV_p^{(l)}, \quad (3)$$

where $\mathbf{u} = [u(x, y, t), v(x, y, t), w(x, y, t)]'$, ρ and ρ_{pzt} are the density of the composite and the piezoelectric elements, respectively, V_s and $V_p^{(l)}$ are the volume of the composite and the l^{th} piezoelectric element, respectively, N_{pzt} is the total number of piezoelectric elements bonded to the bi-stable composite, the overdot ($\dot{}$) symbol implies differentiation with respect to time, and the superscript ($'$) indicates the transpose operation.

The total kinetic energy is thus written as:

$$T = T_{st} + T_{pzt}. \quad (4)$$

The strain energy for the wing-shaped bi-stable composites is obtained by adding up the contributions of the symmetrical and unsymmetrical parts of the lay-up, yielding:

$$U_{st} = \int_{-L_x^S}^0 \int_{-\frac{L_y}{2}}^{\frac{L_y}{2}} \frac{1}{2} \left(\left[\begin{array}{c} \epsilon^o \\ \kappa \end{array} \right]_s' \left(\begin{array}{cc} \mathbf{A} & \mathbf{B} \\ \mathbf{B} & \mathbf{D} \end{array} \right)_s \right) \left[\begin{array}{c} \epsilon^o \\ \kappa \end{array} \right]_s dy dx \\ + \int_0^{L_x^U} \int_{-\frac{L_y}{2}}^{s_x + \frac{L_y}{2}} \frac{1}{2} \left(\left[\begin{array}{c} \epsilon^o \\ \kappa \end{array} \right]_U' \left(\begin{array}{cc} \mathbf{A} & \mathbf{B} \\ \mathbf{B} & \mathbf{D} \end{array} \right)_U - \left[\begin{array}{c} \mathbf{N}_T \\ \mathbf{M}_T \end{array} \right]' \right) \left[\begin{array}{c} \epsilon^o \\ \kappa \end{array} \right]_U dy dx, \quad (5)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\epsilon}^o = [\epsilon_{xx}^o \ \epsilon_{yy}^o \ \epsilon_{xy}^o]'$ is the vector of in-plane strains, $\boldsymbol{\kappa} = [\kappa_{xx} \ \kappa_{yy} \ \kappa_{xy}]'$ is the vector of bending strains, and \mathbf{A} , \mathbf{B} , \mathbf{D} , represent the well-known extensional, bending-extension coupling, and bending stiffness matrices, respectively, and \mathbf{N}_T and \mathbf{M}_T are the thermal expansion force and moment vectors, respectively [12]. The subscripts s and U indicate symmetric and unsymmetric lamination, respectively. The planform dimensions defining the integration domain are given by the span of the unsymmetric region, L_x^U , the length of the symmetric region, L_x^S , the chord length at the clamped edge, L_y , and the chord length of the tip, t_p . The leading-edge slope defining the wing-shaped (tapered) form is given by $s = \frac{t_p - L_y}{L_x}$. A detailed geometrical description of the planform is presented in Fig. 2. The total strain is given by $\epsilon_{ij} = \epsilon_{ij}^o + z\kappa_{ij}$. Note that the symmetrical part does not have resulting thermal stresses. The nonlinear extensional strain and

Figure 2: Planform defining the domain of integration for the bi-stable wing.

bending curvatures, ϵ_{ij}^o and κ_{ij} , respectively, are given by:

$$\epsilon_{xx}^o = \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial x} \right)^2, \quad (6)$$

$$\epsilon_{yy}^o = \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial y} \right)^2, \quad (7)$$

$$\epsilon_{xy}^o = \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial w}{\partial x} \frac{\partial w}{\partial y}, \quad (8)$$

and,

$$\kappa_{xx} = -\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2}, \quad (9)$$

$$\kappa_{yy} = -\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial y^2}, \quad (10)$$

$$\kappa_{xy} = -2\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x \partial y}. \quad (11)$$

A state of plane stress is assumed for the considered structures, thus the components of the stress and strain vector for piezoelectric material are related by the constitutive relations:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \sigma_{11} \\ \sigma_{22} \\ \sigma_{12} \\ \mathcal{D}_3 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} c_{11}^E & c_{12}^E & 0 & -e_{33} \\ c_{12}^E & c_{22}^E & 0 & -e_{31} \\ 0 & 0 & g_{12}^E & 0 \\ e_{33} & e_{31} & 0 & \epsilon_{33}^S \end{pmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \epsilon_{11} \\ \epsilon_{22} \\ \epsilon_{12} \\ E_3 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (12)$$

where σ_{ij} is total stress due to a strain in the i -direction acting on the j -direction, ϵ_{ij} is mechanical strain due to a deflection in the i -direction acting on the j -direction, \mathcal{D}_3 is electrical displacement in the 3-direction, E_3 is the electric field in the 3-direction, c_{ij}^E is the elastic modulus due to a strain in the i -direction acting on the j -direction, e_{ij} is the piezoelectric constant relating the poling direction i with the strain in the j -direction, and ϵ_{33}^S is the permittivity coefficient relating the electrical displacement in the 3-direction with the poling

direction of the piezoelectric material, respectively. The superscripts E and S denote that the relevant parameters are measured at constant electric field and constant strain, respectively. Given the plane stress state, the piezoelectric strain energy and the internal electrical work are given by:

$$U_{pzt} = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{l=1}^{N_{pzt}} \int_{V_p^{(l)}} \mathbf{S}'_p \mathcal{T} dV_p^{(l)} + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{l=1}^{N_{pzt}} \int_{V_p^{(l)}} E_3 D_3 dV_p^{(l)}, \quad (13)$$

where \mathbf{S}_p is the vector of strains, \mathcal{T} is the vector of material stress. The poling and extension directions of the piezoelectric elements, 3, coincides with the in-plane x-direction, consistent with the MFC actuators that are employed. The total strain energy for the system is thus written as:

$$U = U_{st} + U_{pzt}. \quad (14)$$

2.2 Equilibrium Configurations

The room temperature static equilibrium shapes are obtained by minimising the potential energy of the laminate U_{st} . Polynomial shape functions are used to approximate the static displacements, given by:

$$u^o(x, y) = \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^N a_{ij} x^i y^{j-1}, \quad (15)$$

$$v^o(x, y) = \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^N b_{ij} x^i y^{j-1}, \quad (16)$$

$$w^o(x, y) = \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^N c_{ij} x^{i+1} y^{j-1}, \quad (17)$$

where $u^o(x, y)$, $y^o(x, y)$ and $w^o(x, y)$ are the mid-plane displacements defining the static equilibrium shapes, $a_{ij} x^i y^j$, $b_{ij} x^i y^j$, and $c_{ij} x^i y^j$ are the shape functions on each coordinate direction, and, $N \times N$ gives the total number of shape functions used on each expansion. Continuity of the displacement to account for the interaction of the symmetric and unsymmetric parts of the laminate is imposed by:

$$u_S^o(0, y) = u_U^o(0, y), \quad (18)$$

$$v_S^o(0, y) = v_U^o(0, y), \quad (19)$$

$$w_S^o(0, y) = w_U^o(0, y), \quad (20)$$

$$\frac{\partial w_S^o(0, y)}{\partial y} = \frac{\partial w_U^o(0, y)}{\partial y}. \quad (21)$$

Figure 3: Statically stable configurations of a wing-shaped bi-stable composite.

Substituting Eqns (6)-(11) and Eqns (15)-(17) into Eqn. (5) the equilibrium shapes are found from:

$$\frac{\partial U}{\partial \alpha_i} = 0, \quad (22)$$

where $\alpha = [a_{ij}, b_{ij}, c_{ij}]$ is the vector of generalised static displacements. The stability of the equilibrium points, C_k^o , is obtained by evaluating the definiteness of the associated Hessian matrix, which is:

$$\frac{\partial^2 U_{st}}{\partial \alpha_i \alpha_j} = H_k |_{C_k^o}. \quad (23)$$

Minima of the potential energy indicate statically stable shapes, which are given by equilibrium points with positive definite Hessian matrix. The resulting geometry for the statically stable equilibrium configurations are given by the mid-plane displacements $u_o(x, y, t)$, $y_o(x, y, t)$ and $w_o(x, y, t)$ of the equilibrium points having a positive definite Hessian matrix, which are schematically shown in Figs. 3(a) and 3(b), respectively. Hereafter, all calculations shown in this study occur about the stable equilibria reached at room temperature. It is worth mentioning that the final equilibrium shapes are a function of the composite material properties, lamination sequence, curing cycle, and the dimensions of the initially flat laminate. Hence, these parameters may be optimised to achieve tailored dynamic and aerodynamic characteristics for a particular application.

2.3 Linear Dynamic Electromechanical Equations

The study of the dynamic behaviour of the wing-shaped piezoelectric bi-stable composites is focused on the low amplitude response around the stable equilibrium configurations. The linear dynamics are obtained as perturbations about the static displacements of the stable shapes given by $u_o(x, y, t)$, $y_o(x, y, t)$ and $w_o(x, y, t)$ [13]. As a result, the linear approximation of the vibration problem reduces to that of a tapered unsymmetrically laminated shell solved for each of the stable equilibrium points.

For the dynamic morphing strategy to control bi-stable composite structures used in this study, knowledge of linear modal properties is sufficient to utilise the resonant actuation technique to achieve full configuration control, as shown in Ref. [4]. For the linear approximation problem following the above described perturbation approach, the membrane strains are recast as:

$$\epsilon_{xx}^o = \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + \frac{w_o}{R_x(x, y)}, \quad (24)$$

$$\epsilon_{yy}^o = \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} + \frac{w_o}{R_y(x, y)}, \quad (25)$$

$$\epsilon_{xy}^o = \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial x}, \quad (26)$$

where the radii of curvature in the x - and y -directions are $R_x(x, y)$ and $R_y(x, y)$, are defined by the large amplitude static displacements of the each equilibrium shape given by Eqn. (22). The bending curvatures remain unchanged as defined in Eqns (9)-(11).

The types of shells studied in this investigation are cantilever tapered bi-stable composites, for which one edge is clamped and the remaining three are free. In this case, the fixed edge imposes an initial curvature at the root. This is only possible due to the used symmetric-unsymmetric lay-up. For this type of linear shell vibration problem, there exists no known closed-form solution [14]. An approximate solution is hence obtained following the Ritz method, for which admissible functions satisfying the geometric boundary conditions for the displacements are chosen. A set of polynomial functions satisfying the above stated boundary conditions are:

$$u(x, y, t) = \sum_{i=1}^M \sum_{j=1}^M a_{ij} x^i y^{j-1} u_{i,j}(t), \quad (27)$$

$$v(x, y, t) = \sum_{i=1}^M \sum_{j=1}^M b_{ij} x^i y^{j-1} v_{i,j}(t), \quad (28)$$

$$w(x, y, t) = \sum_{i=1}^M \sum_{j=1}^M c_{ij} x^{i+1} y^{j-1} w_{i,j}(t), \quad (29)$$

where $u_{ij}(t)$, $v_{ij}(t)$ and $w_{ij}(t)$ are time response coefficients to be determined, $a_{ij}x^i y^j$, $b_{ij}x^i y^j$, and $c_{ij}x^{i+1} y^j$ are the shape functions on each coordinate direction, and, $3 \times M \times M$ gives the total number of degrees of freedom in the dynamic analysis.

In the current formulation, the piezoelectric elements are assumed to be perfectly bonded to the surface of the bi-stable composite and the electric field is taken as the independent variable in the electrical domain. Based on the assumption that the 33 mode electromechanical coupling of the MFC P1 type actuator can be represented by effective 31 mode electromechanical parameters, one electrical degree of freedom per element is sufficient for modelling the electrical response [15]. The electric field of the k^{th} piezoelectric element is thus written as:

$$E_{3effl}(x, y, t) = \frac{v_l(t)}{\Delta_{el}}, \quad (30)$$

where $v_l(t)$ is the generalised voltage time coordinate of the l^{th} piezoelectric element, E_{3effl} is the effective electric field of the l^{th} piezoelectric element and Δ_{el} is the spacing between electrodes [16].

The linear equations of motion for the tapered piezoelectric bi-stable composites are obtained using Lagrange's equations for the mechanical and electrical displacements, yielding:

$$\frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \dot{q}_a} \right) - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial q_a} = F_{aext}, \quad (31)$$

$$\frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \dot{v}_b} \right) - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial v_b} = Q_{bext}, \quad (32)$$

where the generalized coordinates q_a and v_b are the time response coefficients for the mechanical and the electrical displacements. Back substituting Eqns (27)-(30) until Eqn. (1) is reached, yields the electromechanical equations of motion for piezoelectric bi-stable composite wing as:

$$\mathbf{M}\ddot{\mathbf{q}} + \mathbf{K}\mathbf{q} - \mathbf{\Theta}\mathbf{v} = \mathbf{f}_{ext} \quad (33)$$

$$\mathbf{\Theta}'\mathbf{q} + \mathbf{C}_p\mathbf{v} = \varphi_{ext} \quad (34)$$

where \mathbf{q} is the mechanical displacement vector given by $\mathbf{q} = [u_{ij}(t), v_{ij}(t), w_{ij}(t)]'$, \mathbf{v} is the electrical displacement vector given by $\mathbf{v} = [\mathbf{v}_k(t)]'$, \mathbf{f}_{ext} is the mechanical external forcing vector, and $\boldsymbol{\varphi}_{ext}$ is the external electrical forcing vector. \mathbf{M} , \mathbf{K} , $\boldsymbol{\Theta}$ and \mathbf{C}_p , are the mass, stiffness, electromechanical coupling and capacitive matrices of the piezoelectric bi-stable composite, respectively.

Depending on the electrical boundary conditions imposed to the piezoelectric actuators the stiffness matrix, \mathbf{K} , of the system varies. The conditions giving the lowest and highest stiffness are obtained by setting \mathbf{v} and $\boldsymbol{\varphi}_{ext}$ to zero, resulting in the well-known short-circuit and open-circuit electrical boundary conditions [17], respectively. Superscripts E and D are used in the remainder to differentiate a quantity obtained using short- and open-circuit electrical boundary conditions, respectively. The modal characteristics these cases are obtained by studying the homogeneous vibration problem, i.e. assuming no external forcing and a harmonic response of the form $\mathbf{q} = \boldsymbol{\nu}e^{i\omega t}$, where ω is an eigenvalue of the system and i is the imaginary number. The modal properties for each case are thus obtained from the following eigenvalue problem equations:

$$\left(\mathbf{K} + \boldsymbol{\Theta}\mathbf{C}_p^{-1}\boldsymbol{\Theta}' - \omega^{2D}\mathbf{M}\right)\boldsymbol{\nu}^D = 0, \quad (35)$$

$$\left(\mathbf{K} - \omega^{2E}\mathbf{M}\right)\boldsymbol{\nu}^E = 0, \quad (36)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\nu}^D$ and $\boldsymbol{\nu}^E$ are the short- and open-circuit vectors of weighted amplitudes, ω^D and ω^E are the short- and open-circuit natural frequencies. Equations (35) and (36) are solved to obtain eigenvalues of the system, which are equivalent to modal frequencies for the problem at hand. The eigenvalues are used for choosing the input frequency to the actuators in the resonant control strategy, as well as providing upper bounds for the modal frequencies in the design of wing-shaped bi-stable composites. Notice that it is assumed that the voltage source driving the piezoelectric actuators is unaffected by the dynamics of the system, hence the electrical equation given by Eqn. (34) can be dropped and the voltage term in Eqn. (33) becomes the control input to the system. This is an accurate assumption, as conventionally used amplifiers show a low output impedance.

The obtained linear electromechanical equations of motion are useful in two important aspects.

First, given the geometry of the bi-stable composite structure the modal properties, namely natural frequencies and mode shapes, for the electromechanical system can be obtained with Eqns (33) and (34). The mode shapes are obtained by combining the vector of weighted amplitudes $\boldsymbol{\nu}$ with the shape functions used to approximate the out-of-plane displacement given in Eqn. (29). It is worth mentioning that the mode shapes provided by the short- and open-circuit eigenvalue problems produce essentially the same shapes as the stiffness does not undergo large variations with the change of electrical boundary conditions. Second, the generalised coupling coefficient can be studied as a function of the position of the piezoelectric elements allowing for maximisation of the actuation authority for specific modes. These two aspects are investigated in depth in the following sections.

2.4 Mode Shapes

The mode shapes obtained from the short-circuit eigenvalue problem given by Eqn. (35) yield the deformation forms when the wing-shaped composite is actuated at a given natural frequency. This deformation shapes are useful as the resonant control strategy targets the specific natural frequencies that lead to minimum actuation effort for triggering snap-through. For the asymmetric shape given by the planform defining the wing-shape, inspection of the theoretical mode shapes allows for selecting the appropriate resonant frequency to target for triggering snap-through. The mode shapes for stable state 1 and 2, w_{n^s1} and w_{n^s2} , respectively, are obtained using the eigenfunctions produced from Eqn. (35), and plotted in Figs. 4 and 5, respectively. The subscript n indicates the number of the mode shape, $n=1$ for the first mode, where ascending n indicates higher modal frequency.

It can be seen that the first bending mode for each stable state shows the more uniform bending deformation for the first four vibration modes. Previous studies showed that exciting the first bending modes on each state results in the largest deflections being induced in wing-shaped composites [18]. This is expected as bi-stable laminates are lightly damped structures for which the highest deformation is achieved for the low frequency modes. Hence, targeting the first mode with the resonant control strategy results in triggering snap-through with the

(h) w_{4s2}

Figure 4: Theoretical mode shapes for wing-shaped bi-stable composites for the geometry of stable state 1, see Fig. 3(a). a) b) e) f) 3-D view of first four mode shapes. c) d) g) h) Contour of first four mode shapes.

Figure 5: Theoretical mode shapes for wing-shaped bi-stable composites for the geometry of stable state 2, see Fig. 3(b). a) b) e) f) 3-D view of first four mode shapes. c) d) g) h) Contour of first four mode shapes.

least effort. The selection of the optimal position for maximising the authority over a particular mode of the actuators for exerting the resonant control strategy is presented in the following section.

3 Optimal Positioning of Piezoelectric Actuators

A simple optimisation procedure comprising the behaviour of the generalised coupling coefficient as a

function of the position of the piezoelectric actuators is implemented. The actuation strategy followed to apply the configuration control of the wing-shaped bi-stable composites used in this paper is based on inducing resonance of a bending mode to force sufficient deflection to overcome the critical displacement threshold necessary for triggering snap-through. The generalised coupling coefficient provides a measure of the effectiveness a given actuator positioning yields, hence this is employed as objective functions in the optimisation procedure.

The generalised piezoelectric coupling coefficient is defined as [17]:

$$k_{nnsm}^2 = \frac{\omega_{nsm}^{D^2} - \omega_{nsm}^{E^2}}{\omega_{nsm}^{E^2}} \quad (37)$$

where ω_{nsm}^D and ω_{nsm}^E are the open-circuit and short-circuit modal frequencies, respectively, associated to mode n , for stable state m .

In this study the position of the piezoelectric actuators is used as the optimisation parameter, while keeping all other dimensional and material property values fixed. The actuators are positioned parallel to each other separated by a fixed distance, $y_{C.M.}$, as schematically shown in Fig. 6. Thus, the distance from the origin, o , to the edge of the piezoelectric elements, x_{MFC} , fully defines the position of the actuators. This parameter is thus varied for maximising the generalised piezoelectric coupling coefficient, k_{ii}^2 . The variation of the actuators position x_{MFC} is constrained by the dimensions of both the wing-shaped bi-stable specimen and the actuator used for each specific case. The selected dimensions of a wing-shaped specimen considered for demonstration of the concepts herein presented are provided in Fig. 6, while those of the MFC actuator are given in the caption of Fig. 6. Taking into account the taper of the used wing-shaped bi-stable composite and the dimensions of the considered piezoelectric MFC actuator, the possible range of variation for x_{MFC} ranges from 0 to 20 mm. Nevertheless, with the presented approach it is possible to explore the variation of all dimensional parameters for both the planform of the bi-stable composite, and the dimensions of the chosen actuators.

The natural frequencies obtained from Eqns (35) and (36) are substituted into Eqn. (37) to obtain the variation of the generalised coupling coefficient for the first four bending modes of state 1, $k_{ii^s1}^2$, as a function of the position of the actuators. The obtained results, presented in Fig. 7, show the maximum value of the coefficient is obtained for the first bending mode, w_{1s1} . As expected for the cantilevered configuration, this maximum occurs when the actuators are positioned at the root of the wing-shaped composite. As the position of the actuators is moved away from the root, the coupling coefficient decreases for modes w_{1s1} and w_{4s1} , while it increases for mode w_{2s1} . For mode w_{3s1} the coefficient remains unchanged indicating that the actua-

Figure 6: Wing-shaped bi-stable composite lay-up. The position of the MFC is calculated with respect to the frame of reference origin, o mark with \otimes . The dimensions of the used 8557 P1 MFC actuators are 85x57x0.3 mm.

Figure 7: Variation of the generalised coupling coefficient, $k_{ii^s1}^2$, as a function of the position of the MFC edge x_{MFC} for the specimen in state 1.

tors are acting on nodal lines of the associated mode shape, as can be also inferred from Figs. 4(e)-4(g).

Similar results are obtained for the generalised coupling coefficient for the first four bending modes of state 2, $k_{ii^s2}^2$ $i = 1 \dots 4$, as shown in Fig. 8. It can be seen the highest coupling coefficient is obtained for the first bending mode, $k_{11^s2}^2$, when the MFC actuators edges are placed at the clamped root. This coincides with the results obtained for state 1, although the over 3 times larger coupling coefficient achieved in the case of state 2 indicates a higher actuation authority can be expected to be available for controlling the structure in this configuration. A different trend for the coupling coefficients for

Figure 8: Variation of the generalised coupling coefficient, k_{ii}^2 , as a function of the position of the MFC edge x_{MFC} for the specimen in state 2.

the other three modes can be observed for state 2 in comparison to the results of state 1. For modes w_{3s2} and w_{2s2} the coupling coefficient increases as the position of the actuators is moved away from the clamped edge. For mode w_{4s2} , the value of the coefficient remains fairly constant for the studied range.

The results shown in Figs. 7-8 clearly indicate that positioning the actuators closest to the root yields the maximum generalised coupling coefficient, hence resulting in the highest control authority. Furthermore, the mode shapes shown in Figs. 4-5 show that exciting the first bending mode on each stable state produces the most compatible deformation for reaching the critical displacement condition necessary to trigger snap-through. The combination of the two above stated results show that for exerting configuration control with the previously developed the resonant strategy [4] on wing-shaped cantilevered bi-stable composites, a close to the clamp edge position maximising the values for k_{11s1}^2 and k_{11s2}^2 is to be chosen. This theoretical result validates the near the root placement chosen in previous works involving piezoelectric bi-stable composites is proven correct [19–21]. It is worthwhile noticing that the presented approach can be used to maximise the authority to actuate over other modes of the wing-shape structure.

4 Conclusions

The optimisation of the position of piezoelectric actuators for controlling the configuration of wing-shaped bi-stable composites is presented. Natural frequency values for the first bending modes of each stable state are theoretically obtained and used to calculate the variation of the generalised coupling coefficient with respect to the position of the chosen MFC actuators. The generalised coupling coefficient is thus maximised, obtaining the highest possible control authority for inducing resonance of a particular vibration mode. The presented results allow for selecting the position of piezoelectric actuators for controlling the desired state of wing-shaped bi-stable composites with minimum actuation effort. It is worth mentioning that other parameters, such as fibre orientation or piezoelectric to composite thickness ratio, can be used for optimisation of the control authority to obtain further performance gains for the resonant control technique. Furthermore, the presented results are applicable for maintaining a desired configuration of the wing-shaped bi-stable composite when subject to external perturbations.

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